

Formation of Teachers' Readiness to Integrate Exact and Natural Sciences in the Context of Implementing Health-Saving Technologies in the Educational Process

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Abstract: The article examines the issues of integration of exact and natural sciences in the context of the implementation of health-saving technologies in the educational process at all stages of the continuous education system.

Keys words: integration, health-preserving, exact and natural sciences, health-preserving technologies, educational process.

Currently, one of the pressing issues in pedagogical science is the problem associated with the need to ensure health preservation of the younger generation in the education process. Familiarization with literary sources indicates that the ongoing modernization of the content of education, optimization of methods and technologies for organizing the educational process actualizes such concepts as "preparedness" and "readiness" of a teacher to implement health-preserving knowledge in the context of integrating exact and natural sciences at all stages of the continuous education system. In recent years, a system for acquiring health-preserving knowledge in the continuous education system has been developed in Uzbekistan, on the basis of which students develop health-preserving competencies, starting from preschool education up to higher education. The integrative processes implemented in the Republic dictate the need to integrate exact and natural sciences on health-preserving issues, which imposes on teachers the mission of forming readiness for the implementation of health-preserving technologies in the education process. Teachers of exact disciplines (physics, computer science, chemistry, mathematics, etc.) acquire the necessary health-preserving competencies by obtaining information when familiarizing themselves with such biological disciplines as "Age anatomy, physiology and hygiene", "Genetics", "Immunology", "Life safety" and others. At the same time, a special role is played by the effective use of health-preserving educational technologies by teachers, considered both as a qualitative characteristic of any educational technology, its "health safety certificate", and as a set of those principles, techniques, and methods of pedagogical work that implement traditional methods of education, endowing them with a health-preserving feature. This is especially true for physics teachers, who, when considering certain sections of physics, must pay attention to the possibility of their positive or negative impact on human health. In particular, when studying the topics "Atmospheric pressure", "Constant electricity", "Optics", "Thermal conductivity", "Magnetic field", "Body mass", etc. the teacher draws attention to the influence of these phenomena on the vital functions of the body, to the mechanisms of physiological processes occurring in the body, to the maintenance of its homeostasis in changing environmental conditions, to the need to know the influence of these phenomena on the physical health of a person, etc. It is important for physics teachers to know that, according to literary data, factors influencing the health of students are divided into 3 groups:

endogenous (gender, age, hereditary); exogenous (social, economic, environmental, legal) and factors that appear within the educational system (physiological and hygienic, pedagogical, socio-psychological, socio-demographic) [1].

In this context, it is important to implement health-preserving training of future teachers on the observance of the health-preserving principle in organizing the educational process of teachers of natural and exact sciences, taking into account the influence of educational risk factors that affect the performance, physical and mental health of students. It should be borne in mind that the ranking of educational risk factors by significance and strength of influence revealed the following: intensification of the educational process; stressful pedagogical tactics; inconsistency of teaching methods and technologies with the age and functional characteristics of students; irrational organization of educational activities; low competence of teachers and parents in matters of health protection and promotion [1]. It should be known that the educational process in educational organizations exposed to these factors is considered health-consuming [2].

It has been established that at present the material and technical base of educational institutions does not always meet the recommended hygienic requirements (equipment of lecture halls, classrooms for laboratory classes, gyms and physical education grounds), and the observed increased psychogenic loads from teachers with an authoritarian teaching style, the presence of hypodynamia syndrome (low physical activity), the inability of individual teachers to properly organize the educational process and arouse interest in their subject - all this often becomes the cause of the emergence of limited disorders (neuroses), which leads to deterioration of their mental health. In this regard, an important factor is the development of a system for maintaining and developing students' health, providing teachers with a health-oriented educational process in the university, providing for disease prevention, normal functioning of the body; its harmonization with the environment; the student's ability to fully perform basic social functions; complete physical and mental health, social well-being; human adaptation to increasingly complex and changing environmental conditions [3].

Specialists of higher education institutions implementing natural and exact sciences should keep in mind that for students the most significant is the social component of health, including the formation of a system of value relations, including health, readiness for self-determination of life path, as well as social activity in matters of health preservation and the ability to social adaptation. This is caused by the presence of the spread among them of such manifestations of an unhealthy personality as dependence on bad habits, as well as the so-called "manias" (gambling addiction, telephone addiction, computer addiction, television addiction, etc.), behavioral maladaptation, conflict, inadequate perception of the surrounding world, decreased responsibility for maintaining their health and those around them, etc.

In the context of the above, the problem of health-oriented activities of the teacher is actualized, based on three methodological principles: preservation, strengthening and formation of health of students, implemented with the use of health-saving technologies proposed by M.K. Smirnov, contributing to the increase in professional competence of the professorial teaching staff of the university necessary for the successful implementation of health-saving activities [4]. The classification of health-saving technologies includes: medical and hygienic, physical education and health, environmental, as well as life safety technologies, health-saving educational technologies, which, in turn, are divided into organizational and pedagogical, psychological and pedagogical and educational technologies in extracurricular activities. At the same time, socially adaptive and personal development technologies aimed at strengthening the physical and psychological health of students, increasing the resources of physiological and psychological adaptation of the individual, as well as therapeutic and health technologies, including therapeutic pedagogy and therapeutic physical training, ensuring the restoration of the physical health of students, can be used in extracurricular activities.

Thus, the successful integration of exact and natural sciences in the context of increasing health-preserving activities with the use of health-preserving technologies used systematically and comprehensively will undoubtedly contribute to improving the quality of education.

Literature

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